

ROAD observations of the hot RCB star V348 Sgr

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Equipment

- 40cm f/6.8 ODK from Orion Optics, UK
- ASA DDM 85 direct drive mount (ASA Austria)
- FLI ML16803 CCD with UBVRI Astrodon photometric filters
- ~ 320 nights/year since Aug. 2011

Research Highlights

- AR Sco, first white dwarf pulsator (Nature paper)
- J1407 ring system, WD1145 debris system
- Intensive novae observations
- Cataclysmic variables
- Luminous blue variables
- RR Lyr stars
- Hot RCB star V348 Sgr
- **65 + refereed papers with co-authorship can be found on ARXIV searching for Hamsch**

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Questions: e.g. how to interpret the fast minimum in 2014 in terms of dust ejection physics